

PENGEMBANGAN WEBSITE “SUNTING PINTAR” SEBAGAI INOVASI PEMBELAJARAN PENYUNTINGAN BAGI MAHASISWA BERBASIS *LIFE SKILL* DAN *ENTREPRENEURSHIP*

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian adalah mengembangkan media pembelajaran penyuntingan melalui aplikasi “Sunting Pintar”. Aplikasi tersebut merupakan laman interaktif yang digunakan dosen dan mahasiswa dalam pembelajaran penyuntingan. Laman terdiri atas tiga portal, yaitu admin (dosen), editor (mahasiswa), dan pengguna (masyarakat). Metode penelitian menggunakan *constructivist instructional design* yang terdiri atas 4 tahap, yaitu *define*, *design*, *development*, dan *dissemination*. Produk divalidasi oleh ahli bahasa dan praktisi untuk mengukur kelayakan dan kemudian diujicobakan pada mahasiswa. Responden uji coba sebanyak 30 mahasiswa yang mengikuti mata kuliah Penyuntingan dan 10 mahasiswa Jurusan Bahasa Melayu, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Yala Rajabhat University, Thailand. Teknik analisis data yang digunakan adalah deskriptif kualitatif. Berdasarkan hasil validasi dan uji coba, maka disimpulkan bahwa produk berada pada kategori layak untuk diimplementasikan dengan memperhatikan saran dari validator terkait penambahan konten materi penyuntingan dan ilustrasi gambar dalam aplikasi.

Kata Kunci: *entrepreneurship*; kecakapan hidup; *website* Sunting Pintar.

Abstract

The purpose of this research was to develop editing learning media through the "Sunting Pintar" application. The application was an interactive page that was used by lecturers and students in learning editing. The page consists of three portals, namely admin (lecturer), editor (student), and user (community). This research method used constructivist instructional design which consists of 4 stages, namely define, design, development, and dissemination. The product was validated by linguists and practitioners to measure feasibility and then piloted on students. The trial respondents were 30 students who took the Editing course and 10 students of the Malay Language Department, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Yala Rajabhat University, Thailand. The data analysis technique used descriptive qualitative. Based on the results of the validation and testing, it was concluded that the product was in a feasible category to be implemented by taking into account the suggestions from the validator regarding the addition of editing material content and image illustrations in the application.

Keywords: *entrepreneurship*; *life skill*; *Sunting Pintar website*.